

Language Data Spaces

EOSC Entrust Outreach

Workshop 25.2.2026

Martin Matthiesen

Outline

- Data Space: A definition
- Existing Data Spaces
- The Language Data Space
 - Key facts
 - Features
 - Current landscape
 - Outlook

Data Space: What is it?

Interoperable **framework**, based on common **governance principles**, standards, practices and **enabling services**, that **enables** trusted **data transactions** between participants.

Source: Dataspace Support Centre

<https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071251781/1+Key+Concept+Definitions>

Existing Data Spaces

Catena-X (<https://catena-x.net>)

“The first globally trusted and collaborative data ecosystem for the automotive industry”

Catena-X: Eine Abrechnung mit der größten IT-Luftnummer der deutschen Industrie
wiwo.de

German “Wirtschaftswoche”, 31.8.2024:
“A reckoning with the biggest IT scam in German industry”

6 months later...

“Since April 2025, Catena-X registration has been an integral part of the BMW Group's procurement process.”

Source: <https://www.bmwgroup.com/en/news/general/2025/catena-x-connects-digital-supply-chains.html>

The Radar:

<https://www.dataspaces-radar.org/radar/>

25 data spaces out of 235 “in production”

- Self reported
- Unclear how to join
- Often metadata catalogues

The Language Data Space: Key facts

- A project funded by the European Commission
- Currently in testing, version 3.0.0 just rolled out
- Services
 - Public Central Catalogue
 - Prototype Invoicing Component
 - Metadata Import & Creation
 - Exchange Protocols for Cloud Infrastructures
 - The LDS Licensing Framework
 - NLP/AI Services (new feature, not yet in production)
 - Local Logging and Analytics Module
 - Central Monitoring Service - The Observer

The Language Data Space: Features

- Working software
 - Find data (for now: test data)
 - Negotiate download (via machine readable contracts)
 - Initiate download
 - Share data locally
 - Audit trail available
 - Easy to connect to identity management networks

The Language Data Space: Current landscape

- In Academia
 - Academia has federated identity management (eduGAIN)
 - LDS can be easily connected
 - Sharing of restricted language data via CLARIN already established
 - No direct need
- In Industry
 - Industry does not yet have access to federated identity management
 - Generic data sharing a hard sell
 - Example: Polish Large Language Model (PLLuM) project
 - Setting up LDS connector not hard, but
 - requires commitment and resources
 - Identity management to use unclear

The Language Data Space: Outlook

- The LDS and TREs
 - Provisioning of data to storage backend possible
 - No backend for Encryption At Rest (EAR)
 - LDS currently more suitable for less sensitive data (that does not require EAR)
- Summary and next steps
 - LDS showcases what is possible in data sharing
 - Expected to be taken over by ALT-EDIC
 - Uptake by non-academic (and academic) institutions yet unclear
 - TREs as consumers might convince data providers to join
 - But: administrative burden of providers needs to be kept in mind

Kiitos!

Martin Matthiesen

martin.matthiesen@csc.fi

Follow us

[LinkedIn](#)

[Instagram](#)

[Facebook](#)

[YouTube](#)

csc.fi